

PECULIARITIES OF EDUCATION OF PATRIOTIC QUALITIES IN STUDENTS OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN AN INFORMATIONAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: This article highlights the current educational processes of young people in the social life of the digital age, related to a lot of information and open resources on the Internet.

Key words: education, upbringing, information, Internet, digital age, technologies

Peculiarities of the diversity of information flows and the contradiction of information, the mechanisms of implementing the tasks of the system of educating patriots, taking into account the diversity of information, the pedagogical process that can resist the decline of spiritual-educational and moral-psychological opportunities aimed at forming the skills of students in professional educational institutions it is necessary to reveal the essence.

Today, receiving and analyzing information has become an independent area of human life. Information and fake information have become inseparable. The role of technologies related to information processing and transmission, as well as related areas of education, has increased. As one of the forms of artificial intelligence, knowledge engineering, which is a component of the current expert system, is rapidly developing. The speed of information transmission and the role of a large number of diverse information flows, on which all spheres of society and human life, even the structure of consciousness, are directly related.

Computerization and communication have become an integral part not only of work, but also of everyday life. A single information network has been created that allows you to get information about any point of the globe. The virtual environment began to take more and more place in people's lives. All these signs indicate that a qualitatively new era has entered the development of the so-called information society.

When entering the "informed" society, the age-related role of information covering all spheres, diversity and abundance of human activity is emphasized.

Since the human nervous system is a product of a long evolution, it is difficult and painful to adapt to such large-scale changes that take place during the life of one generation (first of all, changes in the field of technology), because none of our ancestors who passed before us faced such situations.

Nowadays, social and cultural cycles are interrupted, this interruption is manifested in rapid changes of cultural traditions and values; a person mixes several cultural periods during his lifetime. In the course of socio-cultural changes, in the conditions of time compression, man and society lose their footing.

At the heart of these changes is the phenomenon of information diversity. The diversity category was formed under the influence of Western European and American scientists. The diversity of information flows is explained by the following signs:

- orientation of information to influence the needs of society and the information consumer for social, cultural, political and other purposes (formation of public consciousness, immediate distribution and reception of information about socially significant changes in existence; organization of information and conflict, clarification of public opinion, public administration dissemination of decisions made by institutions, maintaining the vital tone of society at the level of intergroup relations, solving problems of a business nature (advertising, newsletter references, etc.));
- various means of information preparation (computer network, Internet, audiovisual media, information services, electronic streams, press publications, etc.);
- a set of tasks to be solved by the state and society regarding information policy, etc. In this regard, it is suggested to view the information streams placed in the press and special advertising genres as a combination of informative and analytical texts; environment of social debate; reputation, effectiveness of specific activity; interpersonal communication on the subject is covered.

The question of the positive and negative consequences of information diversity arises. If until recently Internet users formed some kind of social group, community, today network activity has already become an integral part of the daily life of most of the inhabitants of the globe. The Internet has included everything, all kinds of information, communication, and on the one hand, it has become an alternative to existence, which reflects the world and, on the other hand, embodies a lot of things that are not typical for real life. It is associatively or thematically distinguished by the fact that the contents of the texts contained in it do not correspond to reality and virtual existence. The Internet is the main source not only of information, but also of lies and fake information. It is full of fake information, advertisements, experts' comments and evaluations copied

from the original content, the main purpose of which is to draw users into pointless confrontation and foreign ideas.

Variety of means of information production (computer networks, Internet, audiovisual media, information services, electronic information streams, press publications, etc.); fulfillment of specific tasks of the state and society regarding information policy. In this regard, it is recommended to review information flows from press publications, advertisements and other publications of an important informational and analytical nature; environment of social discussion-discussion; authoritative effect of specific activities; was characterized by interpersonal communication issues.

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